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**REALISING A 'RIGHT' TO
RESEARCH IN NIGERIA
AND SOUTH AFRICA: THE
ROLE OF THE EXECUTIVE
ARM OF GOVERNMENT**

DSLL WORKING PAPER SERIES 2023/3

DATA SCIENCE LAW LAB

Post-print: Okorie, C., 2023. Realising a 'right' to research in Nigeria and South Africa: The role of the executive arm of government. *Journal of Comparative Law in Africa* (In Press).

*REALISING A 'RIGHT' TO RESEARCH IN NIGERIA AND SOUTH AFRICA: THE ROLE
OF THE EXECUTIVE ARM OF GOVERNMENT
Chijioke Okorie**

Abstract

Development agendas and plans such as South Africa's National Development Plan 2030 and Nigeria's National Development Plan 2021 – 2025, indicate the need for, and benefits of, development research to sharpen countries' innovative edge and to contribute to global scientific and technological advancement. Recent scholarship has highlighted the positive impact on national development of copyright exceptions allowing for the right to research. This can be in the form of either a complete defence to copyright infringement, or, as user rights. However, the realisation of a right to research has been limited by a copyright legislative framework that may be challenging to interpret. Other hinderances to realising the right to research are limited access to courts for interpretation due to limited resources and also as a result of the inherent institutional limitations of courts to consider only the case pleaded by parties before them. In this environment, the role of the executive arm of government in driving the realisation of a right to research is crucial. Yet, there been no executive action to provide for the much-needed clarification to concretise and promote the right to research to actualise development goals. Focused on Nigeria and South Africa, this paper explores the duties imposed on the institutions of executive government and applies administrative law principles to indicate a policy toolkit within copyright statutes that may be deployed to realise a right to research and engender guidance for researchers, copyright owners, users and audience of research.

Keywords: research; copyright; copyright exceptions; executive government; administrative law; Nigeria; South Africa

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Introduction

Development agendas and plans, such as the World Intellectual Property Organisation (WIPO) Development Agenda, African Union Agenda 2063, South Africa's National Development Plan 2030 and Nigeria's National Development Plan 2021 – 2025,¹ indicate the necessity of research and its benefits for development, as understood in this paper as a “right to research”.² Research, as an activity, is crucial for countries to sharpen their innovative edge and contribute to global scientific and technological advancement.³ Recent scholarship has highlighted the positive impact on national development of copyright exceptions that facilitate a right to research, whether in the form of a complete defence to copyright infringement⁴ or as a “user right” within the copyright framework.⁵

Within the field of copyright law, research is understood in the context of copyright exceptions prevalent in many parts of the world. Typically, a specific provision within a copyright statute indicates that the unauthorised use of a copyright-protected work for research purposes is not an infringement if such use is considered “fair use” or “fair dealing” depending on the jurisdiction.⁶ However, “research” is a nuanced concept and therefore characterised by subtle shades of meaning. For example, research could involve the reproduction of a copyright-protected work where the researcher was quoting portions of that work. Research could also involve the communication of a given work, its adaptation and/or its distribution. Further, research may also involve the use of informational aspects of a given work as opposed to, or even in addition to, unique, original elements of the work.⁷ Advances in the field of data science which include, for example, text and data mining (TDM) have further complicated this issue. Questions here include whether simple and data mining (TDM) should be considered “research” or whether the intent behind the TDM activity is crucial in categorising it as

¹ See National Planning Commission. National Development Plan 2030: Our future - make it work. (2015), available at https://www.gov.za/sites/default/files/gcis_document/201409/ndp-2030-our-future-make-it-workr.pdf, accessed on 19 March 2023;

WIPO. The 45 Adopted Recommendations under the WIPO Development Agenda, available at <https://www.wipo.int/ip-development/en/agenda/recommendations.html>, accessed on 19 March 2023; Nigeria Federal Ministry of Finance, Budget and National Planning *National Development Plan 2021 – 2025*, available at https://nationalplanning.gov.ng/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/NDP-2021-2025_AA_FINAL_PRINTING.pdf, accessed on 19 March 2023.

² The expression, “right to research” is not construed as a fundamental human right or constitutional right. Indeed, none of the constitutions of the countries under study nor any human rights instruments explicitly recognise a specific “right to research”. However, as scholars such as Oriakhogba and Appadurai have argued that there is basis for the recognition of a specific fundamental right to research. See Desmond Oriakhogba ‘*The Right to Research in Africa: Exploring the Copyright and Human Rights Interface*’ (2023); Arun Appadurai ‘The right to research’ (2006) 4(2) *Globalisation, Societies and Education* 167-177.

³ Ibid.

⁴ Ruth L. Okediji (ed) *Copyright Law in an Age of Limitations and Exceptions* (2017); Karapapa, S. *Defences to Copyright Infringement: Creativity, Innovation and Freedom on the Internet*(2020).

⁵ Niva Elkin-Koren ‘The new frontiers of user rights’ (2016) 32 *Am U Int'l L Rev* at1; Maurizio Borghi 2021 ‘Exceptions as users’ rights?’ in E Rosati (ed) *The Routledge Handbook of EU Copyright Law* (2021) at 263-280.

⁶ Flynn, S., Schirru, L., Palmedo, M. & Izquierdo, A., 2022. ‘Research exceptions in comparative copyright’ available at <https://digitalcommons.wcl.american.edu/research/75/>, accessed on 19 March 2023.

⁷ Marivate, V., Sefara, T., Chabalala, V., Makhaya, K., Mokgonyane, T., Mokoena, R. & Modupe, A. ‘Investigating an approach for low resource language dataset creation, curation and classification: Setswana and Sepedi’ (2020) in *Proceedings of the first workshop on Resources for African Indigenous Languages* at 15–20, Marseille, France. European Language Resources Association (ELRA).; Jerome H. Reichman & Ruth L. Okediji ‘When copyright law and science collide empowering digitally integrated research methods on a global scale’ (2022) 96 *Minn L Rev* at 1362.

research. In this regard, the EU's TDM exception for purposes of scientific research, including the definition of TDM, has been criticised for being unduly broad and relying too much on copyright exception, potentially encompassing the entire realm of data-driven AI.⁸

In essence, the realisation of a right to research within the field of copyright law has been limited by a copyright legislative framework that may be challenging to interpret especially given technological advances,⁹ new modalities of using copyright-protected subject matter, and new avenues and outcomes of research.¹⁰ The right to research is also hindered by limited access to courts for interpretation due to limited resources and also the inherent institutional limitations that confine courts to consider only the cases presented before them.¹¹ Whether focusing on defences or rights, research exceptions, like other copyright exceptions are matters of public policy.¹² As a matter of public policy and given constitutional provisions, the issue of research (exception) implicates or necessitates government action or involvement. In this environment, the role of the executive arm of government in driving the realisation of a right to research is crucial, as argued in this paper. Yet, there has not been any executive action providing much-needed clarification to promote a right to research in order to actualise development goals.

Legislation provides an avenue for the exercise of rights to conduct and access the results of various kinds of research. For instance, section 12 of the Copyright Act 1978 (South Africa) provides an exception to copyright protection, allowing for fair dealing with works for purposes of research. Provisions such as this might suggest a certain indicate some right or, at the very least, authorisation to to lawfully conduct research using copyright-protected material. But, given the emergence of new channels, modes, formats and platforms for both conducting and disseminating research outcomes,¹³ the practical enforcement of such a right to research would require interpretation and, potentially, a concrete framework for implementation.¹⁴

This paper advances two primary arguments: First, it argues that the executive has a primary constitutional duty to implement and/or 'execute' statutes and that to do so, it must engage in an interpretative exercise not only to identify its duties but to also understand the purpose of the statute in order to effectuate it. Second, it contends that the executive should, barring reasons of national security and related factors, articulate and/or communicate to the public its interpretation of statutory provisions, enjoying substantial discretion in selecting the

⁸ Thomas Margoni & Martin Kretschmer 'A deeper look into the EU text and data mining exceptions: Harmonisation, data ownership, and the future of technology' (2022) 71(8) *GRUR International* at 685-701.

⁹ *Ibid.*

¹⁰ NDP 2015 (n1) at 326-327.

¹¹ Okorie, Chijioke 'Fair use or fair dealing in Africa: The South African experience' in *Developments and Directions in Intellectual Property Law* (forthcoming) (2023).

¹² Sadulla Karjiker 'Should South Africa adopt fair use? Cutting through the rhetoric' (2021) 2 *Journal of South African Law/Tydskrif vir die Suid-Afrikaanse Reg* at 240-255; Rosati, E. *Originality in EU copyright: full harmonization through case law* (2023); Samuelson, P. 'Justifications for copyright limitations and exceptions' in *Copyright Law in an Age of Limitations and Exceptions* (2015).

¹³ Research outcomes and outputs are increasingly presented in various formats (including as products and services) and across platforms. Research increasingly also takes place in industrial laboratories, government departments, corporate research units, parastatals, statutory research councils, and NGOs, working **in silos or in collaboration with each other. See NDP 2015 op cit note 1 at 326-327.**

¹⁴ Anel Du Plessis 'The promise of 'well-being' in Section 24 of the Constitution of South Africa' (2018) 34(2) *South African Journal on Human Rights* at 191-208 (arguing that the constitutional right to well-being imposes a duty on the executive to give force to those rights).

media or tools for communicating its interpretation. The rationale for these arguments, especially the second one, is strengthened by the institutional nature of the executive, which understood in this paper, comprises the president, the cabinet, ministerial departments, executive agencies, public independent agencies, regulatory bodies, commissions and government parastatals, each often ascribed specific roles and duties within specific statutes.¹⁵ These two arguments have wide-ranging implications for realising a right to research.

A preliminary conclusion that may be drawn from this investigation is how under-utilised the executive articulation of statutory interpretation has been in the field of copyright in Africa. It is institutionally better positioned than courts when it comes statutory interpretation¹⁶ – not being restricted to cases pleaded by parties and being an integral part of the law-making process – the executive has a greater opportunity to provide statutory interpretation that aligns with statutory text, legislative history, industry/sectoral understanding, and so on. This power can be applied towards realising a right to research in Africa.

This paper explores the critical role that government's use of various communication tools – so-called 'tools of articulation' – can and should play in realising a right to research in Africa. It focuses on Nigeria and South Africa as economically powerful jurisdictions in West and Southern Africa, in order to offer lessons from which other countries in Africa may learn, including determining an interpretation of the "research" exception in copyright law in a way that allows the exception to be a force for development.¹⁷ In this paper, the executive's role in realising a right to research is highlighted by considering both the ascribed statutory functions of the executive body and the interpretative context inherent in the executive's unique institutional position. The executive occupies a role that is respected, constitutionally recognised, and can accord legal certainty.¹⁸ In this regard, the approach taken parallels that of administrative law scholars in their study of statutory interpretation by executive agencies, the practice of executive agencies and the status and enforceability of executive interpretation as distinct lines of enquiry.¹⁹

¹⁵ Other scholars adopt a similar definition. See Oliver N. Fuo 'Constitutional basis for the enforcement of "executive" policies that give effect to socio-economic rights in South Africa' (2013) 16(4) *Potchefstroom Electronic Law Journal/Potchefstroomse Elektroniese Regsblad* at 7; Kevin M. 'Stack purposivism in the executive branch: How agencies interpret statutes' (2014) 109 *Nw UL Revn* at 879-880. This broad understanding of the executive aligns with constitutional delineation.

¹⁶ Jerry L. Mashaw 'Agency-centered or court-centered administrative law: A dialogue with Richard Pierce on agency statutory interpretation' (2007) 59 *Admin L Rev* at 896.

¹⁷ See Fuo op cit note 15 at 34 (arguing that the executive has wide discretion on how it exercises its delegated powers and could use regulation, policy, code or strategy).

¹⁸ Ibid at 488- 489 (arguing that the executive's exercise of delegated powers should have the force of law); Rebecca Ingber 'Interpretation catalysts and executive branch legal decision-making' (2013) 38 *Yale J Int'l L* at 361 (arguing that "the executive's interpretation of its national security authority is therefore extremely significant and can often serve not only as one step in an inter-branch interpretive dance, but as lawmaking itself").

¹⁹ Fuo op cit note 15 at 487-488; Mashaw op cit note 16 at 893; Lourens Du Plessis 'The (re)systematization of the canons of and aids to statutory interpretation' (2005) 122(3) *South African Law Journal* at 591-613; Marius Van Staden 'The theoretical (and constitutional) underpinnings of statutory interpretation' in *Select Essays on Governance and Accountability Issues in Public Law* (2020) at 1-32; Singh, A. *The impact of the constitution on transforming the process of statutory interpretation in South Africa* (PhD thesis, University of KwaZulu-Natal, 2016).

In order to achieve its stated objectives, this paper is structured in three main parts. The first part draws from the work of administrative law scholars on the executive's statutory interpretation, implementation (instruments) and concretisation of legislative provisions to provide a constitutional, statutory and institutional basis for government's role in realising a right to research. It illustrates that when the executive seeks to give effect to legislative provisions, it engages in an interpretative exercise which could provide much-needed certainty regarding those legislative provisions. The second part provides an overview and explanation of a selection of tools that are available to the executive in the field of governance (generally referred to in this paper as "tools of articulation") and then demonstrates their relevance to the field of copyright. The second part also goes on to present two case studies, one from Nigeria and one South Africa to demonstrate that such tools of articulation could realise a right to research in Africa, and that many such tools have the force of law and could provide guidance to researchers, audience or users of research and also, to institutions. The third part of the paper explores the implications of the availability and use of these tools of articulation in realising a right to research, by proposing some guiding principles and developing some interpretative paths that may be applied to realise the right. The conclusion suggests that the executive's use of tools of articulation as proposed in this paper could be beneficial in realising a right to research in Africa.

The executive's mandate in realising a right to research

Here, the discussion examines the constitutional, statutory (copyright statute), and institutional basis for the role of the executive in realising a right to research. It begins with an exploration of the nature of the general mandate of the executive under the constitution of Nigeria and South Africa, respectively, to implement and/or "execute" the law. This is followed by a discussion of the duty imposed on the executive under the copyright statutes in Nigeria and South Africa. The last section of this part highlights the institutional basis for the executive's role in realising a right to research.

Constitutional basis

Section 5(1) of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria extends the executive powers of the Federation, which vests in the president (and ministers of the government of the Federation or officers in the public service of the Federation, on the president's behalf) to the *execution and maintenance* of the Constitution, to all laws made by the National Assembly and to all matters with respect to which the National Assembly has power to make laws. Such matters include copyright by virtue of Part 1, Second Schedule to the Constitution.

Section 7(2) of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa requires the state to respect, protect, promote and fulfil the rights in the Bill of Rights which, in terms of section 8(1), "applies to all law, and binds the legislature, the executive, the judiciary and all organs of state". Section 84(2) stipulates that the president is responsible for, inter alia, assenting to and signing Bills, referring a Bill back to the National Assembly for reconsideration of the Bill's constitutionality, and/or referring a Bill to the Constitutional Court for a decision on the Bill's constitutionality. The president exercises the executive authority together with other members of the cabinet by, inter alia, implementing *national legislation*, developing and implementing

national policy, co-ordinating the functions of state departments and administrations, and preparing and initiating legislation.²⁰

To implement laws enacted by the legislature, the executive branch of government must engage in statutory interpretation.²¹ The executive branch must, of necessity, accord some (interpretative) meaning to a statute in order to “execute” and/or “implement” it. This is also the case with the entirety of copyright statute including provisions relating to the research exception.²²

In essence, implementing a statute involves interpreting it. The executive must offer (even if to itself or internally) some interpretation or understanding of the purpose of that statute, the scope of its powers, the principles that could inform its actions, and the scope of options available to it in performing its duties amongst others.²³ Whether one terms these activities as “statutory interpretation” or as “policymaking”, the executive must have an understanding of a statute in order to adopt a policy position and practically implement that statute. As such, even if there is some objection to the term used,²⁴ there is implicit consensus that policy choices are to be understood as interpretative.²⁵ The point is that there is constitutional support (in Nigeria, South Africa and other jurisdictions) for the executive’s interpretation and implementation of its statutory duties through instruments of its choice.²⁶ These constitutional provisions on the powers of the executive show that statutory interpretation is not the exclusive preserve of the judiciary.

Statutory basis

Having explored the constitutional basis for the executive’s role in realising a right to research, the next possible basis is statutes, in this case, the relevant copyright statute. A key feature of statutes is the vesting of authority on specific executive bodies or institutions to take actions that have binding force.²⁷ The copyright statutes are no different. As discussed below, they confer powers on various executive bodies to make regulations, license, advise, investigate, recommend, coordinate resource management, and so on. Apart from vesting powers in the minister, the commission, amongst others, to make rules, adjudicate, license, permit, advise

²⁰ See section 85(2).

²¹ Fuo op cit note 15 at 16; Du Plessis op cit note 19; Trevor Morrison ‘Constitutional Avoidance in the Executive branch’ (2006) 106 *Colum L Rev* at 1211).

²² Morrison op cit note 21 at 1190-1191 arguing that the executive has constitutional authority to interpret the laws it is charged with executing. See also, Mashaw op cit 16 at 897-898 on what interpretation entails.

²³ Ibid.

²⁴ For example, Richard J Pierce ‘How agencies should give meaning to the statutes they administer: A response to Mashaw and Strauss’ (2007) 59 *Admin L Rev* at 204-205 (arguing that the construction of, and reference to, statutes by agencies is mere policymaking); Fuo op cit note 15 at 4 (making reference to “executive policies” with reference to what the executive does to give effect to legislative provisions); Karjiker op cit note 12 (generally referring to “policy preferences”).

²⁵ Ibid. Also, Du Plessis op cit note 14.

²⁶ Fuo op cit note 15 at 19-20; Oluwapelumi Odunayo Osadola & Phebe Oluwatoni Ojo ‘Use of executive orders in Nigeria by the executive branch of government in time of emergency’ (2020) 2(3) *Britain International of Humanities and Social Sciences (BIOHS) Journal* at 669-678; Elijah Oluwatoni Okebukola & Abudulkarim A. Kana ‘Executive orders in Nigeria as valid legislative instruments and administrative tools’ (2012) 3 *Nnamdi Azikiwe University Journal of International Law and Jurisprudence* at 59-68; Mashaw op cit note 16 at 895; Stack op cit note 15 at 879.

²⁷ Ibid.

and investigate, another key feature of all statutes is that they also impose an inherent duty to exercise the powers granted.²⁸ This is discussed below.

Copyright-based executive powers in Nigeria

In the case of Nigeria, the executive bodies directly involved with matters of copyright law, including research as a copyright-facing activity, are the Minister of Justice (i.e., the Attorney-General of the Federation),²⁹ and the Nigerian Copyright Commission established by virtue of section 77 of the Nigerian Copyright Act of 2022.

Nigerian Copyright Commission (NCC): The NCC has a governing board consisting of a chairman who shall be a person *knowledgeable in copyright matters*, the Director-General of the NCC, one representative from the Ministries of Justice and Education, one representative each from the police force and the customs service and six other persons representing authors of each category of protectable subject matter, namely literary works, artistic works, musical works, cinematograph films, sound recordings and broadcasts.³⁰

The range of powers (and role) of the NCC under the Copyright Act is quite broad and extensive.³¹ In relation to the NCC's powers as they pertain to a right to research, section 78(1) of the Copyright Act grants the NCC powers, inter alia, to "enlighten and inform the public on matters relating to copyright", to "be responsible for such other matters as relate to copyright in Nigeria", and to "exercise any other functions and duties as may be necessary for the attainment of the object of this Act".³²

The Attorney-General of the Federation (AGF): The AGF recommends the person to be appointed as Chairman of the Governing Board and the person to be appointed as the Director-General of the NCC. It also appoints the representatives of authors who must be members of the Governing Board³³ and authorises the NCC to create regulations regarding the rental and exhibition of copyright works,³⁴ among other responsibilities.³⁵ More significantly, the AGF is empowered under section 99 of the Act to give directives to the NCC regarding any of the functions of the NCC under the Act. The NCC has a duty to comply with such directives. In 2019, the AGF utilised this power which was available under section 50 of the now repealed Copyright Act of 2004 to intervene and resolve the longstanding issue regarding the approval

²⁸ Stack op cit note 15 at 890-891 (arguing that "many statutes build the expression of a duty [to implement the powers granted] into the vesting of power").

²⁹ Per the decision of Nigeria's Federal High Court in *Copyright Society of Nigeria v Music Copyright Society of Nigeria and Ors*, unreported Suit No: FHC/L/CS/1259/2017 (13 February 2018), the Minister of Justice/Attorney General of the Federation (MoJ/AGF) is the Minister envisaged under section 51 of the now repealed Nigerian Copyright Act of 2004 having been designated by the president to oversee copyright regulation in Nigeria. The Copyright Act of 2022 repeals the Copyright Act of 2004.

³⁰ Section 79. Emphasis added.

³¹ See sections 8(2), 17(3), 49(6), 88(2), 88(6)(c) and 89(3).

³² See section 78(1)(d), (g) and h.

³³ Section 83.

³⁴ Section 97(1)(a).

³⁵ For other powers of the AGF, see sections 89 (on copyright levies) and 97 (on regulations regarding anti-piracy devices).

of a collecting society – Music Copyright Society of Nigeria (MCSN).³⁶ The AGF directed the NCC to issue MCSN with an operating licence.

Copyright-based executive powers in South Africa

Under South Africa's Copyright Act, the executive bodies directly involved with matters of copyright law, including research as a copyright-facing activity, and as such, being responsible for interpretation, are the Minister of Trade, Industry and Competition;³⁷ along with its appointee, the Standing Advisory Committee on Intellectual Property. The Minister's range of powers and role are quite broad.

Minister of Trade, Industry and Competition: The Minister indicates the countries to which the provisions of South Africa's Copyright Act extend in line with international copyright treaties' principle of national treatment.³⁸ The Minister, in exercising this power, must be *satisfied* that the beneficiary country has made, or will make, reciprocal provisions for copyright owners under South African copyright law.³⁹ It may be argued that in specifying modifications or exceptions to national treatment and in satisfying itself that a non-convention country has made, or will make, reciprocal provisions, the Minister is engaging in some interpretative activity.

The Minister also has quasi-legislative powers. Section 39(a) of the Copyright Act empowers the Minister to create regulations for any matter stipulated in the Act stipulates. These include regulations *permitting* reproduction of a work per section 13 and regulations in regard to the circulation, presentation or exhibition of any work or production per section 45(1). Section 39(b) of the Copyright Act empowers the Minister to make regulations *prescribing* tariffs of fees payable in respect of proceedings before the Copyright Tribunal, *prescribing* the remuneration of advisory committee members appointed under section 40 of the Act,⁴⁰ and *providing* for the establishment, composition, funding and functions of collecting societies.⁴¹ Regulations in respect of these matters are to be made in consultation with the Minister of Finance. However, section 39(d) empowers the Minister to make regulations "generally as to any matter which *he considers it necessary or expedient* to prescribe in order that the *purpose* of [the Copyright Act] may be achieved" (emphasis added). Again, it is argued that, in order to make regulations in a general sense, and more particularly for any matter that the Minister considers necessary or expedient, the Minister must engage in an interpretative exercise to discern the intended *purpose* of the Act.

The Minister is also empowered to *appoint* an advisory committee to make recommendations on amendments to the Copyright Act, and has powers to refer any matter to the Advisory Committee.

³⁶ Letter of the Minister of Justice and Attorney General of the Federation (MoJ/AGF) to the Director General of NCC, N.I.149/1, 22 March 2017 (on file with the author).

³⁷ Section 1(1): "'Minister' means the Minister of Trade and Industry".

³⁸ See section 37(1).

³⁹ See section 37(3).

⁴⁰ Section 37(c).

⁴¹ Section 37(cA).

Advisory Committee: This is a statutory committee and a body in its own right and may, as stipulated in section 40(3), *make recommendations* in regard to any amendments to the Copyright Act. The Committee is permitted to *constitute subcommittees* and *appoint* other persons as members of such subcommittees.⁴² It may also *call* any person to assist it with or to investigate matters relating to amendments to the Copyright Act and/or matters referred to it by the Minister.⁴³ As indicated above, the Minister determines the remuneration of the members of the Advisory Committee in consultation with the Minister for Finance. Two aspects highlight the significance of this advisory committee in terms of its potential in realising the right to research: the composition of its membership and the reliance of its authority on the actions of the Minister.

Pursuant to the appointment powers of the Minister, a Standing Advisory Committee on Intellectual Property (SACIP) was established in 2000 with Judge Farlam as Chairperson.⁴⁴ It appears the Committee did not advise on any matter during its term, perhaps because there was no referral from the Minister. The term of that Committee has since expired and has not been renewed nor has a new committee been established (even in the face of an ongoing Copyright Amendment Bill process).⁴⁵ As stipulated under section 40(1)(a), it is compulsory for a judge or a senior advocate of the Supreme Court of South Africa to serve on the Committee. The other members are persons determined by the Minister. None of these copyright statutory provisions explicitly stipulates any right to research or a research exception to the executive. However, there is ample evidence of discretionary and comprehensive powers to implement the copyright statute and give effect to its purpose, which will be further be elaborated upon subsequently.

Institutional basis

The argument that the executive engages in statutory interpretation, with constitutional support, offers so much promise, particularly in view of its institutional uniqueness and capacities, and its access to expertise, if not its own expertise.⁴⁶ The executive, and particularly its agencies, is typically involved in the drafting of the statutes they implement. Unlike the judiciary, both the executive and parliament are elected and are more intimately associated with statutory purpose and legislative intent.⁴⁷ As a result, the executive has a “very nuanced sense” of legislative aims and statutory purpose⁴⁸ and its statutory interpretation takes place in a much more “information-rich environment” than does statutory interpretation in the courts.⁴⁹ This is

⁴² Section 40(4).

⁴³ Section 40(5).

⁴⁴ See Government Communications (GCIS) Statement on Cabinet meeting of 20 September 2000 (Preprint), available at <https://www.gcis.gov.za/content/newsroom/media-releases/cabinet-statements/statement-cabinet-meeting-20-september-2000>, accessed on 19 March 2023. See also, Standing Committee on Intellectual Property <http://www.thedtic.gov.za/legislation/legislation-and-business-regulation/statutory-committees/standing-advisory-committee-on-intellectual-property/>, accessed on 19 March 2023.

⁴⁵ Karjiker, S. Anton Mostert Chair of Intellectual Property Law (2023) Written submissions on Copyright Amendment Bill B13B-2017. Anton Mostert Chair of Intellectual Property Law, available at <https://blogs.sun.ac.za/iplaw/files/2023/02/Written-submissions-on-CAB-2023-WC-Final.pdf>, accessed on 19 March 2023.

⁴⁶ Stack op cit note 15 at 884.

⁴⁷ Morrison op cit note 21 at 1242.

⁴⁸ Ibid at 1240.

⁴⁹ Ibid.

true in South Africa, as well as in Nigeria, where the NCC and Department of Trade, Industry and Competition have and still are actively leading the process of copyright legislative reform. The executive branch has can sponsor and promote bills before the legislature. By presenting draft legislation and appearing before and corresponding with the National Assembly or parliamentary portfolio committees, these executive bodies are both more familiar and closely connected with the considerations that shaped the statute's drafting and should be better able to place certain parts of the legislative record in the proper context. According to Morrison, this “informational superiority” can make otherwise ambiguous statutory language clear.⁵⁰ The executive, through its constitutional positioning has both close interaction with, and access to, legislative process and history, which it is able to leverage in the process of statutory interpretation for policy implementation.⁵¹

The executive, and specifically its agencies, have the responsibility to set the policy agenda, develop policy and promote necessary reforms. When parliament passes legislation, the executive takes these statutes forward through implementation. This responsibility may sometimes be quasi-regulatory or quasi-judicial but, in all cases, it has a wider, more general and public application than court decisions.⁵² In particular, the executive has on its side, a plethora of resources of statutory meaning, which may not be readily available to the courts. Moreover, the interpretative context of the judiciary differs considerably from that of the executive.⁵³ Unlike the judiciary whose interpretative context depends on and defers to the caseit, the executive has better,holistic understanding of the statutory purpose.⁵⁴

The legal and institutional architecture of the Nigerian and South African copyright executive, including the players and decision-making mechanisms within that architecture support the position that the executive not only engages in an interpretative exercise as a matter of course but that it also has the capacity and institutional expertise to realise statutory purpose through articulation. These executive bodies and agencies are headed by copyright specialists, populated by expert staff members and/or have direct access to experts, with capacity for technical analysis.⁵⁵ For example, as previously pointed out with respect to Nigeria, the Chairman of the NCC Governing Board is statutorily required to be a copyright expert and a large proportion of members of the NCC Governing Board must be representatives of authors from each category of protectable subject matter.⁵⁶ These executive bodies are therefore in a better position to know about the state of the industry, the scope of its reliance on other sectors, and the economic impact of any new rule.

Executive bodies not only have subject-specific expertise, but they also have “procedural flexibility” in the choice of medium utilised to implement statutory provisions. Again, as has been shown, executive bodies can employ regulations (as stipulated explicitly by the statutes),

⁵⁰ Morrison op cit note 2006 (n21) p.1241.

⁵¹ Ibid. See also, Fuo op cit note 15 at 12.

⁵² Ambrose Onyisi Ekpu & Patrick Ikechukwu Iwocha ‘Powers of the executive and legislature in budget making process in Nigeria: An overview’ (2017) 57 *JL Pol’y & Globalization* at 44. According to Mashaw, “[b]ecause agencies are responsible for agenda setting, policy development, enforcement, and maintenance of the political legitimacy of their programs, the agencies’ responsibilities far outstrip reviewing courts’ responsibilities in relation to those same statutory provisions”. See Mashaw op cit note 16 at 902.

⁵³ See Stack op cit note 15 at 889.

⁵⁴ Ibid.

⁵⁵ Ibid.

⁵⁶ Section 35.

policy documents, guidelines, comments and other forms of communication with varying degrees of binding force, to implement statutory provisions and purpose. Furthermore, because of their duty of accountability to the legislature through reports and obligatory appearances in response to summons from the legislature, and to the judiciary when their decisions are subject of judicial review, executive bodies are in prime position to implement statutory provisions and purposes in a way that benefits society. Decisions to implement copyright provisions including copyright exceptions involve matters of public policy, which the executive acting in conjunction with the legislature as per constitutional mandates is best placed to determine.⁵⁷ Moreover, the executive can access expertise and input by soliciting public comments on any of its proposed implementation actions. Real-life examples of this abound across various fields and jurisdictions where the executive has published requests and/or notices for public comments on its proposed actions.⁵⁸ For constitutional, statutory and institutional reasons, the executive has a much greater chance and expertise in actualising or realising a right to research. The rest of this paper proceeds on that basis.

Realising a right to research: Implementation equals interpretation equals articulation

Admittedly, the mere recognition of an obligation to enforce or execute the law does not necessarily indicate *how* that obligation is to be undertaken. Specifically, except in cases where the relevant statute prescribes regulation or notice, it is not explicit how statutory provisions are to be implemented, including whether the executive must explicitly (in spoken and written word) or implicitly, by action execute the law. Even where there is explicit statutory indication as to the medium of execution or implementation, the nitty-gritty in terms of the contents of such medium is at the discretion of the executive and based on its understanding of statutory purpose.⁵⁹ This leaves the executive with a wide discretion in terms of the tools with which to concretise statutory provisions.⁶⁰ This part argues that, in practice, the executive's interpretation or implementation works by articulation. It argues that whatever the executive interpretation, it should be publicly communicated (i.e., *articulated*).⁶¹

Communication studies and administrative law are rife with the tools and platforms that are specifically used by the executive to convey their position on matters under their regulatory and/or administrative control.⁶² This paper explores some of these tools – referred to here as “tools of articulation”. These tools are suggested bearing in mind that they serve the purpose of realising the right to research although some (or even most) of them are of no legal consequence.⁶³

Tools of articulation

To the extent to which the very nature of the day-to-day work of the executive branch of government requires them to address various issues that understanding and interpretation and

⁵⁷ Karjiker op cit note 12 at 248-249; Stack op cit note 15 at 904.

⁵⁸ Stack op cit note 15 at 909.

⁵⁹ Fuo op cit note 15 at 24.

⁶⁰ Ibid. See also Morrison op cit note 21 at 1238.

⁶¹ Fuo op cit note 15 at 487; Morrison op cit 21 at 1258.

⁶² Fuo op cit note 15 at 14 referring to “policies, plans, programmes and strategy” as ways to concretise statutory provisions.

⁶³ Ibid at 2. See also, Morrison op cit note 21 at 1244-1246.

an assertion of the government's legal position on a particular issue.⁶⁴ Whether their understanding of the legal position on a particular issue is kept confidential or articulated in public does not take away from the fact that that happens. The argument here is that it should be asserted publicly, especially when it comes to research exception and indeed various copyright exceptions, because they not only help right holders to understand the limits of their copyright protection, but they also enable users and the general public to understand what they are allowed or not allowed to do with copyright protected subject matter. Accordingly, tools of articulation are tools that allow the executive to publicly assert their position on any matter of legal interpretation. Tools of articulation can promote consensus, for example, where the government is taking a position informed by unifying points of scholarly positions. Tools of articulation impact significantly on the implementation of statutory provisions and purpose. Identifying tools of articulation and understanding their impact is therefore essential to informing public behaviour and influencing policy agenda.⁶⁵

“Signing”, “rejection” or “reservation” statements

In democratic societies, the executive, specifically the president is an integral part of the legislative process. When the legislative branch passes a Bill, such Bill is transmitted to the president for their assent, rejection or reservation. In both Nigeria and South Africa, Bills must be assented to by the President in order to become law. In South Africa, Bills assented to by the president do not automatically become law. Before a new Act comes into force, the president must declare the Act's commencement date in the *Government Gazette*. Furthermore, the president may, if they have reservations as to any provisions of a Bill, send it back to parliament with the stated reservations.⁶⁶ In each instance, the president's decision may be accompanied by statements providing further information as to the purpose of and executive plans regarding implementation. In this regard, presidential statements accompanying a Bill provide an avenue for the executive to indicate its position and interpretation of statutory provisions.⁶⁷ The significance of such statements as a tool of articulation is illustrated below.

Communications/reports to treaty and national law-making bodies

Another tool of articulation is the submission of compliance or other communications to a treaty body in terms of specific international obligations. In this regard, various international copyright instruments mention the committees or other bodies to which member states may submit compliance and periodic reports on measures that they have taken to implement their treaty obligations in relation to copyright. The level and extent of compliance have been discussed in the literature⁶⁸ but this paper only explores the outcomes of the reporting commitments as a tool of articulation of government position with respect to a particular copyright issue.

⁶⁴ Ingber op cit note 18 at 367.

⁶⁵ Ingber op cit note 18 at 377.

⁶⁶ See <https://pmg.org.za/page/legislative-process>, accessed on 19 March 2023. See also, section 79 of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa.

⁶⁷ Morrison op cit note 21 at 1244-1246. See also Kelley, C.S. & Marshall, B.W. 'Going it alone: The politics of signing statements from Reagan to Bush II' (2010) *Social Science Quarterly* 91(1) at 168-187.

⁶⁸ See, for example, Olusesan Fasan 'Commitment and compliance in international law: A study of the implementation of the WTO TRIPS agreement in Nigeria and South Africa' (2012) 20(2) *African Journal of International and Comparative Law* at 191-228.

South Africa's engagement with other countries and international bodies over its copyright obligations is handled primarily by the Department of Trade, Industry and Competition. Nigeria's is handled by the NCC per the Copyright Act. The executive prepares reports to the relevant treaty bodies and is the entity that communicates with the treaty-making bodies.⁶⁹ Reporting or communication with treaty bodies is largely proactive rather than reactive, because the obligation to report to treaty bodies is usually inherent and set by the treaty bodies in relation to the provisions of the specific treaty. Therefore, nations already know ahead of time when they are required to make reports, and thereby communicate their position or interpretation of the effect of international obligations on local laws.⁷⁰ In the case of South Africa and Nigeria, both have signed and ratified, or are in the process of ratifying, several copyright and related treaties that include periodic reporting requirements.

Moreover, treaties make provisions that permit communication from member states to the relevant bodies and institutions established by those treaties. Also in this regard, South Africa's communication to the WTO TRIPS Council on both the TRIPS waiver and the three-step test for exceptions and limitations offers a good example of this tool in action and is discussed below. Both South Africa and Nigeria have had to prepare and issue compliance reports to the World Trade Organisation (WTO) regarding the TRIPS Agreement.⁷¹ These reports offer both an avenue and platform for the executive to articulate their understanding and interpretation of the relevant legislative provision.⁷² Articulation in the form of communication to treaty bodies can offer a forum for decision making that permits significant input from experts, offers room for interaction between governments and civil society and the general public.⁷³

The above applies *mutatis mutandis* to reports to parliament as required in the case of South Africa in terms of section 92(3)(b) of its Constitution.⁷⁴

Press statements/ published speeches and notices

Published speeches offer another tool of articulation that can be deployed proactively and strategically to showcase a chosen policy path.⁷⁵ Because of the preparation that largely proceeds most government speeches and the careful consideration of who is chosen as the speechmaker, published speeches by the executive have a great degree of legitimacy.⁷⁶

Publicly delivered speeches create a kind of internal precedent going forward, at least among executive officers and officials with respect to the issue in question. Speeches are a more malleable tool, than, say, a response to litigation, because there is significant control by the executive officials organising, writing, drafting and delivering the speech in question. Because of the proactive nature of speeches, they also allow the executive to carefully think about what they want to communicate, think about the scope of their powers, and indicate a

⁶⁹ Ibid.

⁷⁰ Ingber op cit note 18 at 396.

⁷¹ Fasan op cit note 68.

⁷² Ingber op cit note 18 at 397.

⁷³ Ibid.

⁷⁴ Section 92(3)(b) of the Constitution provides that "members of the cabinet must provide Parliament with full and regular reports concerning matters under their control".

⁷⁵ Ingber op cit note 18 at 397-398; Morrison op cit note 21 at 1249.

⁷⁶ Ingber op cit note 18 at 399.

position that will satisfy a broad audience and deliver it at the right time. Therefore, it is suggested that the executive should be amenable to delivering speeches if they understand their significance and impact and the control that they have over the narrative on a given issue.⁷⁷

Further, the internet provides an accessible platform for published speeches.

Like other tools of articulation, speeches are accepted as the consolidated view of a specific government agency on a specific issue. Consequently, they carry a considerable measure of weight in influencing decisions of people and businesses, perhaps even more so than judicial precedent that is often only applicable to the specific parties involved in the court case. Courts are constrained in their rulings to the case presented by the respective parties before them. Unlike other tools of articulation like litigation responses or treaty reports/communications, speeches possess a much wider, all-encompassing application to persons, situations and circumstances. Speeches are usually drafted and delivered in such a way that they are accessible to all members of society, both in terms of language, meaning and content.⁷⁸

Litigation response by executive bodies

Where the executive's action or inaction with respect to a given issue is challenged in court, the executive's court filings naturally assert its understanding of the specific legal interpretation of that particular issue. Within their briefs of argument, addresses to court, and their processes filed in court, the executive allows the public to see what the executive's understanding of a particular legal provision is on the issue. Prior to adopting a position on the matter, the executive would have considered that matter internally and arrived at a position, approach, or strategy for the litigation. The heads of argument filed by the Minister of Trade, Industry and Competition in *Blind SA v Minister of Trade, Industry and Competition and others* serve as a good example and are discussed, below.

Articulation made in the course of defensive litigation is reactive rather than proactive because the government is reacting to processes filed by the applicant in the case.⁷⁹ The executive's position and interpretation are largely dictated to by the case filed by the applicant or complainant, as well as pressures such as time constraints, external enforcement, and others, given their substantial reliance on the court's calendar and the need to come up with a position as quickly as possible. In *Blind SA v Minister of Trade, Industry and Development and others* the reactive nature of defensive litigation forced the Minister to declare views critical issues such as the scope of the exceptions for people with disabilities, the scope of disabilities covered by the exception, who is to be regarded as beneficiary persons, who are to be regarded as authorised entities, the propriety of first amending the copyright legislation before ratifying the Marrakesh Treaty, and even the scope of exceptions concerning appropriate action when a statutory provision is declared unconstitutional.⁸⁰ Thus, the position of the executive on these important legal questions of copyright law were largely formed, not through proactive tools of

⁷⁷ Ibid at 401-402.

⁷⁸ Ibid.

⁷⁹ Eleonora Rosati 'What does the European Commission make of the EU copyright acquis when it pleads before the CJEU? The Legal Service's observations in digital/online cases' (2020) 45(1) *European Law Review* at 67-99.

⁸⁰ See paras 29-32.

articulation or the normal channels of decision making in government, but through the litigation strategy process.⁸¹

Litigation or defensive litigation is not only reactive, but also constrained to the legal issues set out by the parties in the specific litigation. *Blind SA vs Minister of Trade, Industry and Competition and others* demonstrates that the impact of tools of articulation is informed largely by the unique nature of that specific tool, the issue being articulated, the articulator themselves and the circumstances of articulation.⁸²

Other tools of articulation

Apart from the above-listed tools of interpretation, other tools of articulation, such as the executive's legal opinions, memos, notices, communications, tweets, policies, and guidelines exist. The nomenclature of such tools does not matter as much as their effect and enforceability.⁸³ The list of tools of articulation is by no means intended to be exhaustive. They only represent a fraction of the many ways in which the executive can communicate its interpretation and understanding of a particular statutory provision for the benefit of the public. As technology advances, various tools of communication with varying degrees of impact will continue to emerge and will be available to the executive. Public articulation of executive statutory interpretation is ideal because it is difficult, if not impossible, to access and assess confidential or informal legal interpretation.⁸⁴ In the case of realising a right to research, confidential articulation of the position or legal interpretation on the question of research will not do. By publicising its articulation, the executive offers a basis for either legislative or judicial clarification.⁸⁵ Conversely, by hiding or failing to verbalise their interpretation and implementation, the executive loses the opportunity to be transparent, to engage in public participation and to provide guidance to the public. The need for articulation is even greater when the courts have not reached any conclusion or articulation on the matter, whether because the matter or issue is non-justiciable or because it is an "underenforced" norm.⁸⁶ Research like

⁸¹ Ingber op cit note at 18 at 375.

⁸² See also, Ingber op cit note 1788 at 376.

⁸³ Fuo op cit note 15 at 28 argues that "The nomenclature of the instrument used by the executive when it exercises delegated legislative powers should therefore not automatically determine the legal effect thereof". See also, Steytler, N. 'The legal instruments to raise property rates: Policy, by-laws and resolutions' (2011) 26(2) *Southern African Public Law* at 484-496.

⁸⁴ Ingber op cit note 18 at 377-378 commenting on the difficulty in assessing confidential or simply informal legal interpretation and arguing for "formal crystallization" and "public declarations". See also, Dorota Mokrosinska 'Why states have no right to privacy, but may be entitled to secrecy: A non-consequentialist defense of state secrecy' (2020) 23(4) *Critical Review of International Social and Political Philosophy* at 415-444; Trevor W Morrison 'Constitutional alarmism' (2011) 124(7) *Harvard Law Review* at 1688-1749.

⁸⁵ Morrison op cit note 21 at 1238.

⁸⁶ For example, Nigeria's fundamental objectives and directive principles of state policy (dealing with socio-economic rights) contained in Chapter 2 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria are non-justiciable. See Rhuks Ako, Ngozi Stewart & Eghosa O Ekhatior 'Overcoming the (non) justiciable conundrum: The doctrine of harmonious construction and the interpretation of the right to a healthy environment in Nigeria' (2016) *Justiciability of Human Rights Law in Domestic Jurisdictions* at 123-141. See also, Morrison op cit note 21 at 1224 asserting the concept of "judicially underenforced constitutional norms" so-called because they are constitutional norms that may be formally justiciable but that receive relatively little (or poor) judicial enforcement.

other copyright exception is a judicially underenforced statutory norm across the subject jurisdictions.⁸⁷

It is of course left for the executive body to decide, depending on the significance of the particular issue to specific classes or members of society, what tools or tools of articulation they decide to use to communicate their position.

Illustrating executive articulation in the copyright field

This section demonstrates how the executive has given effect to and/or exercised its powers in the field of copyright in Nigeria and South Africa. It further highlights how executive's processes and actual articulation of its interpretation contribute to meaningful implementation of copyright statutory provisions. As Fuo argues with respect to the socio-economic rights contained in the South African Constitution, rights are abstract entitlements which become meaningful entitlements only when government adopts legislation, policies, plans and programmes to give them effect. Without these processes of translation, the socio-economic rights remain vague guarantees'.⁸⁸ Although it may be difficult to draw broad conclusions from the jurisprudence in both countries on the effect of utilising tools of articulation because most often the courts do not base their decisions on the tools of articulation themselves,⁸⁹ the impact and utility of tools of articulation is evident from a several occurrences within the copyright field in both countries.

The executive and copyright collective management in Nigeria

As indicated above, both the NCC and the AGF have powers that involve statutory interpretation and articulation of the copyright statute. In the area of copyright collective management, the Copyright Act (Nigeria) requires the NCC to make regulations to regulate the establishment and activities of collective management organisations (CMOs). Furthermore, the NCC has used directives and press releases as tools of articulation to further explain to CMOs and the general public its interpretation of the scope of its powers to regulate the activities of CMOs in Nigeria.⁹⁰ Additionally, the press releases and directives served to educate the public and guide decisions related to the Copyright Society of Nigeria (COSON). They outlined how

⁸⁷ Okediji, R.L., 2006. The international copyright system: Limitations, exceptions and public interest considerations for developing countries, available at https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/iteipc200610_en.pdf at 1-2, accessed on 19 March 2023; Daniel J. Gervais 'Making copyright whole: A principled approach to copyright exceptions and limitations' (2008) 5 *U Ottawa L & Tech J* at 1; Robin Wright 'The "three-step test" and the wider public interest: Towards a more inclusive interpretation' (2009) 12(6) *The Journal of World Intellectual Property* at 600-621; Ruth L Okediji 'The limits of international copyright exceptions for developing countries' (2018) 21 *Vand J Ent & Tech L* at 689.

⁸⁸ Fuo op cit note at 15 at 487.

⁸⁹ Judicial reviews largely focus on actual interpretation as opposed to tool used. See Morrison op cit note 21 at 1198.

⁹⁰ See Afam Ezekude Text of press briefing by the Director General, Nigerian Copyright Commission, Mr Afam Ezekude, on the dispute in the governing board of Copyright Society of Nigeria Ltd/Gte (COSON). Nigerian Copyright Commission, 19 April 2018, available at <http://www.copyright.gov.ng/index.php/news-events/item/427-textof-press-briefing-by-the-director-general-nigerian-copyright-commission-mr-afam-ezekudeon-the-dispute-in-the-governing-board-of-copyright-society-of-nigeria-ltd-gte-coson>, accessed on 18 March 2023; Bob Aroture, Nigeria News | Press Briefing by Copyright Commission on Dispute in Governing Board Of COSON in *Nigerian Law Intellectual Property Watch Inc.*, 1 May 2018, available at <https://nlipw.com/nigeria-news-press-briefing-by-copyright-commission-on-dispute-in-governing-board-of-coson/>, accessed on 18 March 2023.

the activities of COSON had contravened relevant provisions of the Copyright Act and the CMO Regulations ultimately leading to the decision to revoke its operating licence.⁹¹ This instance and NCC's use of press statements and directives as tools of articulation demonstrate the scope of the NCC's powers in the field of copyright collective management, as well as the purpose of CMO regulations, without the need for judicial pronouncement.

The executive and copyright reform in South Africa

The ongoing copyright reform in South Africa offers another good example of how the executive's engagement with, and use of, various tools of articulation have made the abstract provisions of the copyright statute more meaningful.

There is consensus that copyright reform truly began in South Africa with the then Department of Trade and Industry (now Department of Trade, Industry and Competition) establishing a Copyright Review Commission (CRC) to assess artists' concerns regarding royalty distribution, payment and unfair contractual terms.⁹² Given that the same Judge Farlam headed both the CRC and the Standing Advisory Committee on Intellectual Property (SACIP) established in 2000, it is quite plausible that the establishment of the CRC was influenced by, or based on, the advice of the SACIP. The CRC report including recommendations on how to address various copyright issues contributed significantly to the formal drafting of the Copyright Amendment Bill.⁹³ What is important to note for current purposes is that the CRC report has remained a reference point for the far-reaching reforms contained in the Copyright Amendment Bill and has influenced submissions of public agencies, private entities, and individuals on the Copyright Amendment Bill.⁹⁴

Since the presentation of the Bill before Parliament, the Bill has gone through several iterations. For purposes of this paper, the focus is on the roles played by various executive bodies in interpreting the scope and limitations of the existing copyright statute and deciphering what needs to be done to address challenges posed by the statute. The following actions utilising various tools of articulation are relevant: the communication issued by the executive in 2020 to the World Trade Organisation's (WTO) Council for Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS Council), titled "Intellectual property and the public interest: The WTO TRIPS Agreement and the copyright three-step test" (henceforth, the 'IP and public interest communication');⁹⁵ the communication issued by the executive in 2020 titled 'Waiver from certain provisions of the TRIPS Agreement for the prevention, containment and treatment of COVID-19' (henceforth, the "TRIPS waiver communication").⁹⁶

⁹¹ Ibid.

⁹² Nicholson, D. 'The Copyright Amendment Bill: Its genesis and passage through Parliament' (2019), available at <https://infojustice.org/archives/41167>, accessed on 19 March 2023.

⁹³ Ibid.

⁹⁴ See submissions and comments on the Copyright Amendment Bill on the website of Parliamentary Monitoring Group, available at <https://pmg.org.za/bill/705/>, accessed on 27 September 2023.

⁹⁵ See World Trade Organisation. Intellectual property and the public interest: The WTO TRIPS Agreement and the copyright three-step test: Communication from South Africa (2020). Document number: IP/C/W/663.

⁹⁶ See the Original waiver text: India and South Africa. Waiver from certain provisions of the TRIPS Agreement for the prevention, containment and treatment of COVID-19: Communication from India and South Africa (2020). Document number: IP/C/W/669.

The IP and public interest communication were issued to consult WTO member states on the flexibility available to member states in crafting copyright limitations and exceptions within the principles and objectives of the TRIPS Agreement. For the present purposes, what is significant about the communication is that it offered some interpretation and/or understanding that “fair use and fair dealing exceptions *per se* are not in conflict with the international three-step test, including under the more specific approach that the TRIPS Agreement takes to the three-step test under Article 13”.⁹⁷

Also in 2020, the executive in South Africa (together with India at the time) recommended the adoption of text indicating a waiver from certain provisions of the TRIPS Agreement to ensure that “intellectual property rights ... do not create barriers to ... scaling-up of research, development, manufacturing and supply of medical products essential to combat COVID-19”.⁹⁸ While the eventual text adopted by TRIPS member states differs quite materially from the original proposed text of the waiver,⁹⁹ it is argued that the proposal as communicated and articulated in the waiver text offers further evidence of executive statutory interpretation and articulation of what needs to be done with international copyright treaties and agreements to address pressing health and societal challenges. This evidence extends to the issue of utilising tools of articulation to realise a right to research.

As new events and new developments have so broadened the definitions of “research” to include text and data mining and other forms of technology-enabled research, new questions that states did not necessarily grapple with at the time of negotiating or ratifying the various copyright treaties, arise. These circumstances have called for updating the executive’s understanding of its obligations and the executive’s understanding of how its obligations and treaty and legislative provisions apply to these novel situations or contexts.¹⁰⁰ In this regard, and considering the way in which the outcome of the TRIPS waiver debate and conversation in the international forum have coalesced, all derived from a communication initiated by South Africa and India, there is evidence that communication or articulation is generally significant. While determining the specific impact of the tool may be difficult, the utility of deploying tools of articulation is undeniable.

Realising a right to research in copyright law: possible articulation contents

In instances where the government would like to promote and ensure significant research in a particular sector or across all sectors in a country or, where the executive aims to ensure that copyright law does not unduly hinder research activities, it becomes crucial for them to determine the scope of the research exception and the copyright status of various works. Moreover, , the executive body may need to establish the scope of its legal authority to address these matters comprehensively.

⁹⁷ See IP and public interest communication, para 9.

⁹⁸ See TRIPS waiver communication.

⁹⁹ Tahir Amin & Aaron S Kesselheim ‘A global intellectual property waiver is still needed to address the inequities of COVID-19 and future pandemic preparedness’ (2022) 59 *INQUIRY: The Journal of Health Care Organization, Provision, and Financing*, at 00469580221124821.

¹⁰⁰ Ingber op cit note 18 at 396 pointing out that treaty reporting process offers an opportunity for the executive to “engage in a process of stocktaking and self-examination”.

As established in the preceding sections of this paper, the executive clearly has the legal authority to interpret not just the other provisions of the copyright law and but also to define the concept of “research” and the research exception. This authority is specifically based on its responsibility over all aspects related to copyright in the case of Nigeria, as well as its mandate to make regulations on any matter which the Minister of Trade, Industry and Competition “*considers it necessary or expedient* to prescribe in order that the *purpose* of [the Copyright Act] may be achieved”. In the context of the research exception, the pertinent question relates to the content of any response to these obligations.

‘Research’ in the context of Nigerian copyright law

Unlike South Africa, Nigeria’s research exception is not limited to specific classes of works. Instead, section 20(1)(c) of the Copyright Act exempts from copyright protection any acts covered by copyright protection by way of fair dealing for, inter alia, purposes of non-commercial research. However, what constitutes “non-commercial research” is not defined, creating another interpretative gap that could, as shown in the literature in other fields, jeopardise certain research activities.¹⁰¹

Section 20(1)(n) also exempts from copyright protection, the reproduction for the purpose of research of an unpublished literary or musical work kept in a library, museum or other similar institution to which the public has access. Likewise, communication or making available works and other material not subject to purchase or licensing terms to members of the public for the purpose of research through the dedicated platforms of libraries, educational establishments, museums and archives, is excluded from copyright protection.¹⁰² In the case of archives, libraries, museums and galleries, which make and distribute copies of works for non-commercial purposes as part of their ordinary activities, such copies of works may be used for research on their premises with or without the means of technical equipment.¹⁰³

There is something of a definition of “research” under the Act, but it is restricted to the compulsory licencing of translations and reproductions of literary or dramatic works which have been published in analogous forms of reproduction. Section 31 allows for applications to be made to the NCC for a licence to produce and publish a translation of literary or dramatic works for purposes of research, as well as for teaching and scholarship. Such licences are non-exclusive and are subject to royalty rates fixed by the NCC. Section 34 of the Act stipulates that for the purposes of sections 31-33 of the Act:

(2) —*research* shall not include industrial research or research carried out by bodies corporate not owned or controlled by the Government, carrying on any business.

(3) —*purposes of teaching, research or scholarship* includes all types of organised educational and instructional activities at any level in educational institutions.

¹⁰¹ Dirk Neumann, AV Borisenko, J.A. Coddington, C.L. Häuser, C.R. Butler, A. Casino, J.C. Vogel, G. Haszprunar & P. Giere ‘Global biodiversity research tied up by juridical interpretations of access and benefit sharing’ (2018) 18 *Organisms Diversity & Evolution* at 1-12. See also, Kamau, E.C., Winter, G. & Stoll, P.T. (eds) *Research and Development on Genetic Resources: Public Domain Approaches in Implementing the Nagoya Protocol* at 60-74.

¹⁰² Section 20(1)(r).

¹⁰³ Section 25.

‘Research’ in the context of South African copyright law

In the case of South Africa, “research” is mentioned only once in the Copyright Act and with reference to the fair dealing exception. In essence, the research exception is limited to classes of works similar to countries such as Namibia, Mali and Morocco.¹⁰⁴ Where there is fair dealing with a literary or musical work,¹⁰⁵ artistic work as far as is applicable,¹⁰⁶ broadcasts,¹⁰⁷ and/or published editions,¹⁰⁸ copyright is not infringed for the purposes of research. “Research” nor “fair dealing” are defined in the. This creates an interpretative gap where the gains of research exception are to be realised. In this regard, South Africa’s Copyright Amendment Bill addresses some of these issues but still leaves something of a gap. The proposed section 12A(a)(i) provides that fair use in respect of a work or the performance of that work, for purposes of, for example, research does not infringe copyright in that work. While “research” is not defined in the Bill, the proposed section 12A(b) provides for, inter alia, considerations such as whether the research was for non-profit purposes, when determining whether an act constitutes fair use. Nevertheless, what constitutes “non-profit research” remains undefined.

General and possible features of research

Following from the above, how should the executive agency approach the task of interpreting and articulating the research exception based on its discernment and understanding of the boundaries of the purposes or principles espoused by the relevant copyright statute? Given the basic premises of legislative supremacy in terms of the doctrine of separation of power, it makes sense first to ask whether the legislature offers interpretive directions to the executive in the relevant copyright statutes,¹⁰⁹ particularly given that there is not much by judicial guidance as to the contents and criteria for the executive exercise of powers delegated or stated in statutes.¹¹⁰ According to Stack, there is a “sufficient commonality” in all regulatory statutes to support the claim that regulatory statutes impose a duty upon agencies to interpret the statutes they administer in a purposive manner.¹¹¹ In the context of copyright law in South Africa and Nigeria, this approach allows for the identification of the powers and duties of specific executive bodies and the implications of these responsibilities concerning executive action in respect to research. Furthermore, it enables recommendations on the effective execution of these duties in a purposive manner to realise the right to research.

The interpretation of the research exception and the content of any tool of articulation adopted to give it effect must be reasonable, purposive, balanced and inclusive, taking cognisance of the differences in its impact on different classes of society.¹¹²

¹⁰⁴ Flynn, S., Schirru, L., Palmedo, M. & Izquierdo, A. ‘Research exceptions in comparative copyright’ (2022), available at <https://digitalcommons.wcl.american.edu/research/75/>, accessed on ?????

¹⁰⁵ Section 12(1)(a).

¹⁰⁶ Section 15(4).

¹⁰⁷ Section 18.

¹⁰⁸ Section 19A.

¹⁰⁹ Stack op cit note 14 at 886.

¹¹⁰ See *Blind SA v Minister of Trade, Industry and Competition* supra. See also, Fuo op cit note 14 at 26.

¹¹¹ Stack op cit note 14 at 887.

¹¹² This accords with techniques of executive statutory interpretation proposed by various administrative law scholars. See Morrison op cit note 20 at 1240-1242; Hart, H.M. & Sacks, A.M. *The legal process: Basic Problems*

In the case of reasonableness, it has been argued that a statute (and by extension, executive interpretation and articulation) that discriminates against a large sector of society is not reasonable.¹¹³ Similarly, executive implementation that does not take cognisance of or address adverse effects caused by differences in the economic, social, and status of various classes of society is not inclusive and could therefore be unconstitutional.¹¹⁴ Moreover, executive statutory interpretation cannot override, amend or be in conflict with existing laws.¹¹⁵ On purposiveness, it has been argued that it is the interpretative activity of the executive body that courts review when judicial review applications are made.¹¹⁶ If a teleological interpretation (and/or articulation of statutory interpretation) involves an individual right or other provision limiting executive involvement, the individual whose rights are impacted has the right to approach the court and challenge the executive interpretation. Given the broad and general nature of the copyright statutes, particularly the absence of a definition of “research” as an activity exempted from the scope of copyright protection, the executive’s responsiveness, expertise or access to expertise, and ability to assess a range of views better equip it to adopt a teleological approach to realising the promise of a right to research.¹¹⁷ Given its distinct institutional characteristics,¹¹⁸ the executive branch has a significant role to play in realising a right to research, should it choose to do so.

Scholarly literature and copyright jurisprudence that have attempted to define, describe or explain what “research” means in the context of copyright law, reflect the following understanding of its basic features:

1. Research requires access to information and links closely with fundamental human rights such as the right to science and culture, right to education, right of access to information, etc.¹¹⁹
2. Research cuts across various fields such as science and scientific research.¹²⁰
3. Research may be formal (i.e., undertaken in an institutional or organisational context largely academic),¹²¹ or informal (i.e., where it is undertaken without the intention or expectation of creating new knowledge).¹²²
4. Research requires direct or indirect participation of and sharing with others.¹²³

in the Making and Application of Law (1994).; Stack op cit note 14 and note 17 at 905; Van Staden op cit note 21; Singh op cit note 21.

¹¹³ Fuo op cit note 15 at 18-19.

¹¹⁴ Ibid. See also, *Blind SA v Minister for Trade, Industry and Competition and others* supra.

¹¹⁵ *Akani Garden Route (Pty) Ltd v Pinnacle Point Casino (Pty) Ltd* 2001 4 SA 501 (SCA), para 7.

¹¹⁶ Stack op cit note 15 at 883.

¹¹⁷ Stack op cit note 15 at 876.

¹¹⁸ Morrison op cit note 21 at 1201

¹¹⁹ Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR); United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization’s Recommendation on Science and Scientific Researchers, 2017; Desmond O. Oriakhogba ‘The Right to research in Africa: Making African copyright whole’ in PIJIP/TLS Research Paper Series no 78 (2022), available at https://digitalcommons.wcl.american.edu/research/78_at 9; Armstrong, C. & De Beer, J. *Access to Knowledge in Africa: The Role of Copyright* (2010).

¹²⁰ United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization’s Recommendation on Science and Scientific Researchers, 2017.

¹²¹ National Research Foundation. NRF Engaged Research Framework (2022), available at <https://www.nrf.ac.za/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/NRF-Engaged-Research-Framework.pdf>, accessed 19 March 2023.

¹²² Arun Appadurai ‘The right to research’ (2006) 4(2) *Globalisation, societies and education* at 167-177; *SOCAN v Bell*, [2021] 2 R. C. S. 326 (Canada).

¹²³ Appadurai 2 op cit note 167.

5. Research may be commercial/for-profit or non-commercial/not-for-profit.¹²⁴

Based on the above discussion, there exists a spectrum for interpreting the concept of research, allowing for its confinement or expansion within certain conceptions. In many ways, this poses a dilemma for persons who wish to use copyright-protected materials for purposes of research. Without an understanding or some assurance as to the scope of the research exception, it may be difficult, if not impossible, to conduct research relying on the exception.

Across many fields, the absence of clarity on the scope of exceptions poses a risk that many users are not prepared to take when to using copyright-protected.¹²⁵ It is argued that the executive can and should play a significant role in promoting and realising research. The mandates outlined in the national constitution and national copyright legislation offer various avenues for realising research outcomes. These mandates must be leveraged in many ways, including via communication and articulation tools to promote and guide decision-making on undertaking research and using copyright-protected materials for research purposes.¹²⁶ If the benefits of the research exception are to be realised, the executive has a significant interpretative opportunity to explore.

Conclusion

Understanding of the role of the executive in statutory interpretation and articulation yields several inherent utilities and advantages. Each tool of articulation requires an awareness of its availability, legitimacy and impact, which could or should inform the executive's selection based on the objective that it seeks to achieve, be it a change in policy, a change in policy implementation, or conveying its understanding of and transparency in respect of the legal position with respect to its legal obligations.

These objectives should influence the choice of tools of articulation. In the case of especially contentious matters such as copyright exceptions, where there are strong arguments against legislative flexibility and judicial participation in interpreting such flexibility,¹²⁷ the executive's decision to articulate its legal position or understanding of the boundaries of a given exception may well be the only way to effect constructive change for copyright users and copyright owners. Otherwise, copyright exceptions, including research exceptions may well remain dormant in the pages of the statute books without ever being given in public and private life. Given the institutional limitations of the judiciary in giving effect to copyright statutory provisions, utilising these tools of articulation to realise the right to research within the domain of copyright law, offers more than a way to, as it is said in Nigerian pidgin, *take hold bodi*.¹²⁸

¹²⁴ Oriakhogba op cit note 164 at 10; *CCH Canadian Ltd v Law Society of Upper Canada* [2004] SCC 13 (Canada) para 51.

¹²⁵ Deazley, R. & Stobo, V. 'Archives and copyright: Risk and reform' in CREATE Working Paper Series (2013) DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8373; Stobo, V. 'Copyright and e-learning: A guide for Practitioners' (2018) 39(1) *Archives and Records* at 97-99.

¹²⁶ Du Plessis op cit note 13 at 200-201 asserting a similar position in relation to the environment.

¹²⁷ Karjiker op cit note 11 248-249; Eleonora Rosati 'Copyright reformed: the narrative of flexibility and its pitfalls in policy and legislative initiatives (2011–2021)' (2022) *Asia Pacific Law Review* at 1-22.

¹²⁸ (Something) to tide one over or to support one.

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